

Ubaydullaeva M.K.

*Teacher at Foreign language and literature department faculty of
Foreign Philology National University of Uzbekistan*

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES WITHIN COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH

Annotation: Interactive learning made it possible to consider the educational process not only through the prism of communication, but also as a form of cooperation, cooperation, dialogue, group interaction, exchange of experience, a form of modeling future professional activities. This article explains modern methods of teaching foreign languages within communicative approach.

Key words: modern methods, interactive methods, teaching a foreign language, communicative approach.

Interactive forms of work contribute to the formation, development and improvement of the relevant oral-speech skills, stimulation of communicative activity and speech initiative.

Communication skills and group work skills, acquired through interactive methods of organizing the educational process, largely ensure the social competence of the individual and her achievement of life success.

As T.I. Ermakova and E.G. Ivashkin in his work "Conducting classes using interactive forms and methods of teaching", professional training with the help of interactive technologies allows you to learn how to conduct constructive negotiations;

master the techniques of quickly establishing business contact; improve your verbal and visual image;

master the techniques and techniques of influencing other people in the process of interacting with them;

learn to lead your own line in the implementation of cooperation; to master the skills of positioning, presentation of information, goods and services.

The use of interactive teaching methods contributes to the creation of an educational communication environment that is characterized by openness, interaction of participants, equality of their arguments, accumulation of joint knowledge, the possibility of mutual evaluation and control.

One of the possible ways to develop the professional foreign language communicative competence of future specialists is the use of predominantly interactive teaching methods, which are of great practical importance in the development of foreign language intercultural competence, interpersonal communication, especially in the process of forming the skills and abilities of

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

future professional interaction on an interdisciplinary basis with the integration of humanitarian and technical disciplines.

Interactive methods reflect the basic pedagogical principles of activating foreign language communicative activity:

- the principle of communicative orientation, focused on problem-speech, creative authentic communicative situations, the development of spontaneous response skills in the communication process;
- the principle of integration, which allows the student to independently determine the goal, adequate methods and means of activity;
- the principle of situationally, which models the situations of business linguaprofessional communication of future specialists;
- the principle of contextuality, which provides an educational and professional context for foreign language communication;
- the principle of non-linearity, which involves the simultaneous use of various sources of information and interdisciplinary knowledge;
- the principle of autonomy, which determines the personal responsibility of students in the process of planning and implementing their educational trajectory;
- the principle of interactivity is implemented in the form of an authentic dialogue and interaction with e-learning tools, SMART- education technologies, edutainment technology - learning in the process of recreation and entertainment.

After analyzing the definitions and characteristics of the interactive method of various authors, we synthesized the following on their basis: the interactive method is a way to implement a dialogue, intersubjective, activity interaction aimed at developing foreign language communication skills and mastering both social and professional experience using traditional and innovative teaching aids. As mentioned earlier, any method receives a conceptual justification at three levels: approach, design and procedure, which, in turn, include a number of elements.

Based on the elements proposed by foreign language teachers, we will try to further substantiate the target, content, procedural and control and evaluation components of the interactive method at the design level, within which general goals, special tasks, profile-oriented content are determined, as well as and clarifies the roles of teachers, students and the functions of educational materials, as well as describe the stages of practical implementation at the level of the procedure, within which there is a rational adaptation and use of technical means in the context of time and space, practice-oriented pedagogical technologies and forms of interaction.

So, sharing the point of view of V.A. Demina, we believe that the general goals of using the interactive method are:

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

- the organization of comfortable learning, i.e. the student is comfortable because he is successful and intellectually wealthy;
- activation of students' independence; development of communication skills, the ability to communicate and interact, to defend one's opinion;
- cognitive-activity development; the formation of practical skills, professional competencies, the ability to solve problems collectively and individually;
- development of students' speech; involvement of all students present at the lesson.

Individual goals are mainly determined in accordance with the profile-oriented content of the training program and they can be as follows:

- a) **professional goals:** the ability to inform the client, create and sell a product, draw up a financial report or work schedule for staff, carry out training;
- b) **communicative goals:** the ability to understand the requests, wishes, complaints of the client; request information, describe and offer services;
- c) **sociocultural goals:** the ability to organize communication, considering the rules, norms and traditions of speech and non-speech behavior in the country of the language being studied;
- d) **linguistic goals:** proper linguistic knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, phonetics.

Thus, interactive learning is aimed not only at mastering communication skills, but also at their effective application in the process of social- personal and profile-oriented interaction, which makes it possible to effectively integrate previously acquired organizational, managerial, analytical and creative knowledge and abilities.

At the same time, it should be emphasized that within the framework of interactive learning, each student acts as a full participant in the process of generating ideas and educational knowledge in the process of active interaction, as a result of which they master both typical roles for working in a group: facilitator , encourager , compromiser , harmonizer , emotions speaker , group conscience and business roles: leader , initiator , informer , analyst , evaluator , reality tester , time keeper , recorder , implementer .

Along with this, students master the skills of self-assessment and reflection by analyzing the effectiveness of solving communicative, social and linguistic problems in the feedback mode. In the case of using digital interactive learning tools, control is carried out not only by the teacher, but also by the program, and comments are provided in the form of a dialog box. Thus, students become active participants in subject-subject interaction, less dependent on their teachers in obtaining knowledge and applying the skills and abilities formed.

The main interaction strategy within the framework of the interactive method is the interactive and group form " experiential learning ' , 'learning through action/practice' ' learning by doing ' based on authentic materials, highly

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

interactive scenarios, integration of subject-oriented interdisciplinary content, including the basics of speech communication; psychology; ethics of business communication; basics of conflictology; intercultural communication; basics of financial literacy; human resource management; technique of writing business plans and projects.

By recreating a multifaceted model of reality, the student's social and professional self-identification takes place and the result is instantly obtained in the form of feedback. At the same time, an important role is given to the consolidation of the cognitive and activity components of education.

List of used literature:

1. Anthony, E.M. Approach, Method, and Technique / E.M. Anthony // English Learning. – 1963. – Vol. 17. – P. 63-67.
2. Bandura, A. Social Learning Theory / A. Bandura. – New York: General Learning Press, 1977. – 46 p.
3. Ellis, R. Classroom second language development / R. Ellis. – Oxford: Pergamon, 1984. – 350 p.
4. Faria, A.J. Developments in Business Gaming: A Review of the Past 40 Years/ A.J. Faria [et al.] // Simulation & Gaming. – 2009.
5. García-Carbonell, A. Simulation/gaming and the acquisition of communicative competence in another language / A. García-Carbonell [et al.] // Simulation & gaming. – 2001. – Vol. 32 (4). – P. 481-491.

WORDLY
KNOWLEDGE